

CREEP BEHAVIOUR OF GEOMETRICALLY NONLINEAR SOFT CORE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the effects of creep of the core material on the global geometrically nonlinear behavior of sandwich panels under axial and lateral loading conditions. The theoretical model combines the concepts of the hereditary (convolution) integral of viscoelasticity based on the principle of superposition, with the high-order sandwich theory. From the expansion of the relaxation moduli into Prony series, an incremental exponential law that corresponds to the rheological generalized Maxwell model is obtained, and which allows for a step-by-step time analysis that accounts for the change in deformations and stresses with time. The results show that creep of the core can lead to a significant reduction in the global buckling capacity of sandwich panels.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels that are made of metallic or laminated composite face sheets and a soft core find a wide spread use in many engineering applications. Under service conditions, sandwich panels can be subjected to different load scenarios, one of them being axial compression that is combined with lateral loading/effects due to imperfections, self-weight, and other effects. Under such loading, local or global instability issues become very important to be considered in their design. While many efforts have been devoted to investigate the buckling of sandwich panels made with soft or stiff cores under instantaneous loading [1-4], the influence of creep on the geometrically nonlinear behaviour and buckling capacity of sandwich panels has not been investigated.

In many applications, a large portion of the applied load can be classified as a sustained one for certain periods of time, where creep effects become critical because many of the core materials exhibit some level of viscoelastic response under sustained loading. When a sandwich panel with a viscoelastic core is subjected to a combined axial compression and lateral loading, it undergoes increasing lateral and axial deformation with time that is associated with changes in the internal forces and stresses. The change in forces and stresses is because the face sheets are made of materials with different viscoelastic characteristics than those of the core (or from elastic materials). Nevertheless, when the geometric nonlinearity is considered, the change in the deformations and stresses with time might consequently lead to buckling of the sandwich panel under sustained loads that are smaller than the elastic buckling loads. These aspects of behavior need to be investigated for a better and a more reliable design of sandwich panels.

Only few studies appear in the literature regarding the creep response of sandwich panels [5-8]. Yet, most of the existing models use equivalent beam approaches that do not properly describe the interfacial stresses distribution and their concentration near the edges and irregular points, nor their variation with time due to creep. In addition, all these studies focused on the typical bending response of sandwich panels, without addressing their geometrically nonlinear and buckling behavior. Further, they have adopted the effective modulus approach to account for creep, which is more applicable for simple structures that their stresses do not significantly change with time. This is not the case in

sandwich panels due to the interaction between the viscoelastic core and the elastic face sheets, as well as, the change of the internal stresses with time due to the geometric nonlinearity, which require the use of a detailed time-stepping approach for their description.

This paper uses the nonlinear sandwich model described in Hamed and Frostig [9] to analyze the effect of creep on the buckling of sandwich panels made with a transversely flexible core. For brevity, the mathematical formulation of the model, which appears in [9], is not presented here. The theoretical model combines the concepts of the hereditary (convolution) integral representation of viscoelastic solids based on Boltzman superposition principle [10], with the High-Order Sandwich Panel Theory (HSAPT). The face-sheets are assumed to possess membrane and flexural rigidities following Euler-Bernoulli hypothesis and using kinematic relations of large displacements with moderate rotations. The core is assumed to possess shear and vertical normal stiffness only with negligible in-plane rigidity. The hereditary integral is converted into a rheological generalized Maxwell model after the expansion of the relaxation moduli into Prony series. A numerical example that highlights the influence of creep on the buckling of sandwich panels is presented next, followed by summary and conclusions.

2 NUMERICAL STUDY

The geometry and loading of the investigated sandwich beam appear in Fig. 1. The face sheets are made from Aluminum alloy with an elastic modulus of 70.3 GPa. The core is made of cellular polyester foam and its viscoelastic properties follow D'Amore et al. [11] for a foam density of 0.8 g/cm³. In [11], flexural creep results of polyester foam under different temperatures ranging from 20°C to 100°C are reported for a relatively short periods of loading that are less than 3 hours. Using the time-temperature superposition principle, Ramezani and Hamed [12] characterized the viscoelastic properties of the foam core over longer time periods. A temperature of 20°C is chosen for this numerical example, and the compliance function is determined from the test results and the master curve produced in [12]. The relaxation modulus is then assumed as the inverse of the compliance function, and is expanded into a Prony series. Six Maxwell units are used to generate the relaxation modulus, and the relaxation time of the μ -th term in the Prony series expansion is given by:

$$S_{\mu}^n = 0.1 \times 5^{\mu-1} \quad (1)$$

The modulus of each term in the series is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^c &= 97.1 \text{ MPa}; E_2^c = 66.1 \text{ MPa}; E_3^c = 45.1 \text{ MPa}; \\ E_4^c &= 36.3 \text{ MPa}; E_5^c = 36.6 \text{ MPa}; E_6^c = 328.3 \text{ MPa}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Geometry and material properties of a sandwich panel under axial and lateral loads

Due to the lack of data on the viscoelastic behavior of the foam material in shear, the Maxwell constants that correspond to the shear behaviour are assumed to follow the elastic relation (assuming time and temperature independent Poisson's ratio ν_c [10]) with the same relaxation times as those in the normal direction as follows:

$$G_\mu^c = \frac{E_\mu^c}{2(1 + \nu_c)} \quad (3)$$

The sandwich panel is simply supported at the left edge of the lower face sheet with a roller at the right edge. It is subjected to a combination of lateral and axial loading as shown in Fig. 1. Due to the nonlinearity of the problem, a load factor λ that multiplies both the vertical and axial loads simultaneously is used for demonstrating the results. The axial load is chosen to be equal to the global buckling load of the sandwich panel, that was estimated based on Frostig and Baruch [2] and Phan *et al.* [4].

Figure 2: Instantaneous response of a panel: load versus in-plane stress resultants
(Legend: — upper face sheet; - - - lower face sheet)

Figure 3: Distribution of vertical displacement at $\lambda = 0.9$
(Legend: — upper face sheet; - - - lower face sheet)

The instantaneous ($t = 0$) response of the sandwich panel in terms of load factor versus in-plane stress resultants curves appears in Fig. 2. It shows a significant change (softening) in the slope of the curves at a load factor greater than 0.9, which refers to initiation of global buckling of the sandwich panel. Fig. 3 shows the distribution of the vertical displacements at a load factor of $\lambda = 0.9$, which shows a global buckling mode of the sandwich panel.

Two sustained load levels of $\lambda = 0.3$ and $\lambda = 0.6$ are considered for the creep analysis. The loads are assumed to be applied instantaneously at $t = 0$ and to remain constant with time. The time variation of the peak vertical displacement of the upper face sheet for the two load levels is shown in Fig. 4. The results are normalized with respect to the peak instantaneous response. The results reveal an increase with time in the vertical displacement due to creep that is relatively high at the early stages of loading. For a relatively low load level of $\lambda = 0.3$, the rate of deformations start to slow after certain time and becomes very small (almost constant) after about 200 days since first loading, indicating a stable creep behavior with time. However, for the higher load level of $\lambda = 0.6$, the rate of creep increases almost exponentially with time and tends to be unlimited, which indicates global instability of the sandwich panel (creep buckling). These important observations reveal that sandwich panels under sustained loads can actually buckle under load levels that are significantly smaller than their elastic buckling loads.

Figure 4: Normalized creep response of the peak vertical displacement of the upper face sheet obtained with two different initial sustained load levels

3 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the influence of creep of the core material on the global geometrically nonlinear response of sandwich panels, using a nonlinear high-order sandwich panel theory (HSAPT) that accounts for the layered structure configuration through compatibility and continuity requirements between the different layers. An incremental time-stepping approach has been used for the solution in time, based on an exponential creep law that corresponds to the rheological generalized Maxwell model after the expansion of the relaxation moduli into Prony series.

The variation in time of the deformations and the stresses in the core and the face sheets due to creep has been addressed in a numerical study. The results reveal that sandwich panels under a combination of axial loading and some disturbance in the lateral direction, can globally buckle with time due to creep under a sustained axial load that is significantly smaller than the elastic buckling load. In the specific example presented in this paper, creep buckling has been predicted for a sustained load level that equals to 60% of the elastic buckling load. This is an important observation that needs to be considered in the design of sandwich panels because most core materials and especially polymer ones exhibit some level of viscoelastic response.

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